

**PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.**

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Annotation: The point of the current paper is to show a few issues of translation phraseological units from English into Uzbek language considering their linguacultural highlights. The language culture of the individual is shaped at association of wonders "culture of language" and "culture of discourse". In its premise the information on standards of composed and oral discourse, semantic and expressive chances of framework, investigation of excellent workmanship, publicist and some different writings lays.

Keywords: Phraseological units, linguaculturalogy, equivalent, culture of speech, transformation, component.

Learning the vocabulary of any language is always an interesting learning process. Learning English vocabulary can be boring or interesting. Just take the words from the dictionary and teach them how a poem alone can be a boring thing, but if you will, learn words in a group with friends, this process will seem very interesting and not very difficult occupation, process. In the context of interactive learning, knowledge takes on different forms. On the one hand, they represent certain information about the world around them. The peculiarity of this information is that the student receives it not in the form of a ready-made system from the teacher, but in the process of their own activity. The teacher must create situations in which the student is active, in which he asks, acts. Research on the issues of correspondence between societies what's more, people groups

is getting increasingly escalated. In this way, language, being a significant methods of concentrating data about the world, simultaneously goes about as the main sign of a specific group. It is in language that the attitude of individuals, their brain research, customs and mores are most obviously communicated. It is a methods for making public writing, the principle archive of data about a specific group. The public mindset is showed in the impression of the characteristics of life, customs, history and culture, basically phraseological units.

One of the highlights of sayings is to give individuals an appraisal of the target marvels of the real world, consequently communicating the perspective. In the phraseological units is communicated the particular outlook, a method of judgment, the element sees; they show the life, soul and temper, habits and customs, convictions and strange notions. Etymological and social examination of phraseological units is married to outside factors: the set of experiences of the country, its way of life, regular daily existence, and so forth the Study of phraseological units in the etymological furthermore, social perspective assists with explaining, and at times to set up extra semantic shades with public and social semantics. In the idiomatics of the language, that is, in the layer that is, by definition, nationally specific, the system of values, public morality, attitude to the world, to people, to other people are displayed. Phraseological units most clearly illustrate the way of life, geographical location, history, and traditions of a particular community United by a single culture. Issues of translating phraseological units from English into Uzbek, considering their etymological and social attributes, is viewed as quite possibly the most troublesome sorts of interpretation changes. The object of interpretation isn't a language framework as a deliberation, be that as it may, a particular discourse work in another dialect (the first content), based on which another discourse work in another dialect (the interpretation text) is made. The reason for the interpretation is to familiarize the per user (or audience) who doesn't have the foggiest idea about the first language as intently as conceivable with this content (or the substance of oral discourse).

Problems of phraseology are extremely important both for practice and for translation theory; they often present great practical difficulties and arouse great

theoretical interest, since they are related to the difference in semantic and stylistic functions performed in different languages by words of the same real meaning, and to the difference in combinations that such words enter into in different languages. This paper discusses only some of the many problems of translating phraseological units. It is usually accepted to indicate the equivalent of a phraseological unit to a word. However, the theory of complete equivalence is becoming obsolete. This does not mean that phraseological units and words have nothing in common, which is considered by the theory of correlation of certain types of phraseological units and words, which, however, is based on slightly different principles. The most characteristic for phraseological turns of stable combinations of words are in principle equal in meaning to a single word, differing from it, as a rule, by a certain expressive and stylistic coloring. Some idioms are translated with the help of partial (relative) equivalence.

According to E.F.Arsentyeva, such idiomatic expressions are characterized by the minor differences in terms of phraseological expression of the identical semantics that can have a componential or morphological character (Arsentyeva, 1989: 100) The classification of phraseological units also contains the necessary theoretical knowledge for the translator, with which we can identify the phraseological units in the text, then analyze it and, based on the analysis, give the most accurate translation in this context. The most legitimate approach is to consider phraseological units in three aspects: semantic, structural grammatical, and component.

Taking into account the marked levels, the following types are distinguished:

1) phraseological equivalents (full and partial) - phraseological units with identical semantics, structural and grammatical organization and with identical component composition;

Red book - Qizil kitob; The black prince - Qora shahzoda; Black list - Qora ro'yxat; Black diamonds - Qora oltin; Keep quiet - Tinchlik saqlamoq; Make conversation - Suhbat qurmoq; Milk cow - Sog'in sigir; First think, then speak - Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla; The dog bark, but caravan goes on - It hurar, karvon o'tar; Step by step - Qadam ba qadam.

2) phraseological analogs (full and partial) - phraseological units that express the same or similar meaning, but are characterized by a complete difference in the approximate similarity of the internal form; A black hen lays a white egg - Qora sigir oq sut berar. Cut the melon - foydanib olmoq. Put smb/smt to the test - tekshirib ko'rmoq; Red meat - Qo'y go'shti; Take a fancy to smb - Maftun bo'lmoq; Talk turkey - Ochiqdan-ochiq gapirmoq.

3) non-equivalent phraseological units - phraseological units that do not have correspondences in the phraseological system of another language.

To throw up one's cap - do'ppisini osmonga otmoq . Come Yorkshire over smb - Aldamoq, nonni tuya qilmoq Betweenhawk and buzzard - Oila a'zolarini va xizmatkorlar o'rtasidagi o'rinni egallagan inson; Green room - Teatrda artistlarning kiyinadigan, yasanadigan xonasi; Harley Street - Shifokorlar, tibbiyot dunyosi (Londondagi ko'pgina mashxur doktorlar yashaydigan ko'cha); Gretna Green marriage - Uydan qochgan sevishtanlar o'rtasidagi turmush; Since phraseology stands out for its functions in language and speech, it requires a special approach in the translation process. The main difficulty is that no dictionary can provide for all the false uses of phraseology in the context. Phraseological units, similar in internal form in different languages, are not always identical in meaning as a result of their reinterpretation, so you can not rely on the similarity of the figurative basis. But when an expression still retains its connection with the sphere in which it was born, the translator has to look for such a phraseological units in the Uzbek language. Techniques for translating phraseological units vary from complete replacement of imagery to complete preservation of the image in translation. And yet, what is common and characteristic of all is the preservation of imagery in translation. But at the same time, the standard and traditional in the original must be transferred to the standard and traditional in the translation. When translating, it is important to observe the stylistic uniformity of the original text. Along with the absence of a corresponding phraseological units in the Uzbek language, it may seem that an Uzbek phraseological unit that has the same semantic content does not correspond to English. Of course, ideally, you should strive for full equivalence of the means used, but in practice, you often have to sacrifice functional and stylistic correspondence to preserve

expressiveness. It is very important that phraseological substitutions in translation convey the national flavor of the original language. The original, which is full of phraseological phrases, must retain its phraseological richness and quality. Features of the interdependence between language and culture are most clearly reflected in the translation of phraseological units, which are characterized by a high degree of national diversity in form and content. In this case, the most important task of the translator is "the cultural adaptation of such microtexts, which requires translation while maintaining their equivalence, both semantic and affective." (E. V. Blinova, E. G. Doronina, A. I. Efimov, N. N. Zakharova, A. V. Kunin, A. M. Melerovich, L. G. Yudina, etc.). The necessity and expediency of the study are related to their following categorical structural features: broad semantic framework that gives the phraseological unit the ability to relate to many denotations or situations, globalization of nomination, descriptiveness, informational ability, semantic and functional complexity, and expression of connotations special case.

Often a phraseological expression is presented as a complete sentence with a statement, instruction or conclusion. Examples of such phraseological expressions can be proverbs and aphorisms: "O'z uying o'lan to'shaging" - "East or West, home is the best", "the first swallow" - "ilk nishona)". If there are elements of understatement in a phraseological expression, then this will be considered a proverb or catchphrase: "Hamma yaltiragan narsa oltin emas" - "all is not gold that glitters". An alternative source of phraseological expressions is professional speech. Speech cliches also fall into this category of phraseological expressions - stable formulas such as "all the best", "see you again", etc. Many linguists do not consider phraseological expressions to be phraseological units. In their opinion, phraseology is a "storehouse" of any language. Phraseologisms also reflect the history of the people, the originality of their way of life and culture.

In conclusion, translating phraseological units can be considered one of the most difficult aspects of translation. Because it is very difficult to translate phrases that are part of the spiritual heritage and culture of the people. The meaning that one person understands seems to be something new to another. Often it is necessary to find its equivalent in the language of translation in order to discover the full meaning of

phraseology. However, the real process is not just the search for equivalent language correspondence, but a complex, multifaceted process that is influenced by many other factors that subsequently affect the quality of translation, in addition to the skill and professionalism of the translator. A good translator should be familiar with phraseological units and prepare their translation equivalents. But keep in mind that the meaning of a phraseological phrase can have different emotional colors and vary depending on the context in which it is used. Language and speech are so multifaceted that many factors and details need to be taken into account when translating.

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